

ASSESSING THE EFFECTS OF EDGE REFLECTION ON PROPAGATING ACOUSTIC WAVES IN CFRP EPOXY PANELS

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BACKGROUND

- Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) techniques are used for assessing the manufacturing quality of complex parts and for monitoring the life cycle of installed components.
 - Minimize downtime by allowing analysis to be conducted on-site via non-destructive means.
- Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) Techniques
 - Visual Testing
 - Primarily used for detecting macroscopic irregularities.
 - Computed Tomography:
 - Captures internal attenuated X-rays and converts them into electronic signals.
 - Suitable for evaluation of micro-cracks or defects such as voids and pores..
 - Ultrasonic Testing
 - Waves interact with the material (phase-array, c-scan, air-coupled, and laser).
 - For detection of fiber misalignment, localizing porosity, and delamination [Ref. 1.0].
 - Acoustic Emissions
 - Surface vibrations are captured by AE sensor and ultimately digitalized.
 - Most effective method for internal faults and damage type detection in CFRP.
 - AE signals affected by many factors (specimen, waveguide transfer function, sensors transfer function, etc.).
 - Features such as Risetime, Frequency, Energy, and CWT have been studied as the most suitable features for analysis as they carry information about AE source type [Ref. 7.0].

Figure 1. Common Type of Defects Analyzed in CFRP Through NDT Techniques [Ref. 1.0].

HSU-NIELSEN AE SOURCE

- Yields a consistent, replicable, burst acoustic signal if pencil lead is broken at the same angle and position each time.
- Excites a broad range of frequencies.
- Analyzed AE Features: Amplitude, Rise Time, and Energy.
 - Peak Detection Window of 200 μ s.

Figure 2. Acoustic Emission Features.

Figure 3. Hsu-Nielsen Pencil Lead Break (PLB) Technique.

TEST SETUP - OVERVIEW

- ISO Conditions: 20°C, ~1.01 MPa.
- Performed 2 sets of 30 PLBs across three panels (6 plies of 12k twill weave carbon fiber).
 - Sensors were positioned at 8.7 cm and 26.2 cm.
 - Only one sensor was used for the smallest panel.
- Tested five angles: 0°, 22.5°, 45°, 67.5°, 90° for all panels.

Large Panel

Dimensions = 122.2 cm x 122.2 cm x 4 mm.

Medium Panel

Dimensions = 58.7 cm x 58.7 cm x 4 mm.

Small Panel

Dimensions = 34.5 cm x 34.5 cm x 4 mm.

Figure 4. Panel Geometries.

RESULTS – AMPLITUDE (0°/22.5°/45°)

Figure 5. Amplitude Plots for 0°/22.5°/45° Orientation Angles*.

*Datasets for 67.5° and 90° are omitted for clarity. Data for 0°/90° and 22.5°/67.5° was similar.

*[Ref. 8.0, 11.0, and 12.0].

RESULTS – RISETIME (0°/22.5°/45°)

Figure 6. Risetime Plots for 0°/22.5°/45° Orientation Angles*.

*Datasets for 67.5° and 90° are omitted for clarity. Data for 0°/90° and 22.5°/67.5° was similar.

*[Ref. 7.0 and 9.0].

RESULTS – RISETIME (0°-S2-LARGE/MEDIUM PANEL)

Figure 7. Waveform/Wavelet/Risetime Plots for Different Panel Sizes at Orientation Angle of 0° and Sensor Location 2.

*[Ref. 6.0].

RESULTS – RISETIME (22.5°-S1-MEDIUM/SMALL PANEL)

Figure 8. Waveform/Wavelet/Risetime Plots for Different Panel Sizes at Orientation Angle of 22.5° and Sensor Location 1.

RESULTS – ENERGY (0°/22.5°/45°)

Figure 9. Energy Plots for 0°/22.5°/45° Orientation Angles.

*Datasets for 67.5° and 90° are omitted for clarity. Data for 0°/90° and 22.5°/67.5° was similar.

*[Ref. 7.0 and 9.0].

RESULTS – WAVEFORM COMPARISON (LARGE-S1-0°/22.5°/45°)

Figure 10. Twill Weave Pattern [Ref. 2.0].

Figure 11. Large Panel Size Waveforms at Sensor Location 1 for 0°/22.5°/45° Orientation Angles.

*[Ref. 13.0].

RESULTS – WAVEFORM COMPARISON (LARGE-S1-0°/22.5°/45°)

Figure 12. Large Panel Wavelet Transform at Sensor Location 1 for 0°/22.5°/45° Orientation Angles.

*[Ref. 4.0, 5.0, and 10.0].

RESULTS – WAVEFORM COMPARISON (45°-S1-LARGE/MEDIUM/SMALL)

Figure 13. Waveform Plots for Sensor Location 1 at 45° Orientation Angle and Different Panel Sizes.

RESULTS – WAVEFORM COMPARISON (45°-S1-LARGE/MEDIUM/SMALL)

Figure 14. Wavelet Transforms for Sensor Location 1 at 45° Orientation Angle and Different Panel Sizes.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

CONCLUSIONS:

- The risetime is significantly affected by interference patterns between the primary waveform and the reflection.
- Amplitude was generally consistent during all tests performed for the different orientation angles and panel sizes.
- There was a large data spread for energy values at a 0° orientation angle compared to 22.5° and 45° . The highest energy magnitude was at 0° whereas the lowest magnitude was at 22.5° . The energy of a signal which is dependent on the duration and amplitude is significantly affected by reflections.
- Changes in waveform shapes indicate the presence of low and high frequency edge reflections. Interference and attenuation of a signal throughout the visualized plots can affect the AE features discussed above.
- When edge reflections are of concern, features such as energy may be better assessed for just the beginning of the signal.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Implementation of sensor mounts is highly recommended to keep PLB-to-Sensors and Sensor-to-Sensor distances consistent.
 - Preliminary analysis of reflection arrival times is required to evaluate how risetime and energy are affected during post-processing.
 - It is recommended to conduct testing on areas free from nearby bonded or fastened structure (ex. center of skin panel).
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THANK YOU FOR YOUR ATTENTION

Q & A?

EXTENDED GRATITUDE TO DELTA ENGINEERING WHO MADE THIS RESEARCH POSSIBLE.
